

RTM PROCESSING OF GRP-PHENOLIC COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: GRP-phenolic composites are inherently fire retardant and resin transfer moulding (RTM) provides several advantages for their fabrication. To facilitate a better understanding of the issues associated with RTM of acid-catalysed phenolic resole resins, the cure has been studied using isothermal differential scanning calorimetry and viscosity measurements over a range of temperatures. The results are analysed using a series of empirical formulas that describe the changes in extent of reaction, heat flow and viscosity with time and temperature. The total heat of reaction is 347 J.g^{-1} and the consequences for RTM processing are discussed. Also identified is the importance of additional cure above 70°C to achieve satisfactory mechanical properties.

KEYWORDS: phenolic resole resin, GRP-phenolic, DSC, viscosity, RTM, chemorheology

INTRODUCTION

The increasing use of glass reinforced polymer (GRP) composites in the transport, building and maritime industries has required the development of materials with improved performance under fire conditions. Phenolic resins are inherently fire retardant so that on exposure to fire they give longer ignition times, lower heat release rates and a lower amount of smoke compared to polyester, vinyl ester and epoxy resins [1]. The development of low viscosity phenolic resole resins that are curable at low temperatures and pressures using acid catalysts has enabled their application as laminating resins for the production of GRP-phenolic composites [2]. The phenolic laminating resins have several features, including a short pot life, that have limited their use in GRP composites fabricated by conventional methods such as hand lay-up. Resin transfer moulding (RTM), as well as providing general improvements to part quality, including improved fibre wet-out, also offers the advantage of removing the pot-life constraint. RTM processing is thus becoming a preferred method of fabricating GRP-phenolic composites [3].

RTM processing of phenolic resole resins requires special attention to temperature control as there is a temperature ceiling of approximately 90°C imposed by the water that is present in the neat resin and which is generated by the cure reaction [4]. If this temperature is exceeded, the vaporisation of the water can be catastrophic in a closed mould due to the increased internal pressure. The issue becomes more critical because the reaction is exothermic which results in a temperature feedback loop as described by Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The parameters that control the degree of feedback and thus the temperature stability are the chemical kinetics and the reaction exotherm, which are intrinsic properties of the resin, and the heat transfer properties which are dependent on the design and material properties of the mould, the shape and dimensions of the part being fabricated, the reinforcement and the environment. If either the reaction exotherm is too high or the heat transfer is too slow, the heat flow will be positive and cause the temperature to rise and the reaction rate to increase. If this feedback is too strong the temperature will quickly reach the point where water will vapourise.

Another important parameter in RTM processing is the resin viscosity which is dependent on both the temperature and the extent of reaction (Scheme 2), as well as in some cases the shear rate. The viscosity can be related to the resin flow rate and the mould filling pressure using the permeability of the reinforcement and Darcy's law [5].

Scheme 2

Once the chemical kinetics-reaction exotherm-viscosity relationships (i.e. chemorheology) are determined for a particular resin system, RTM simulation software can be used to model the filling of a resin transfer mould if its physical properties are known [5]. Little information exists in the literature on the chemorheological behaviour of low viscosity acid-catalysed phenolic resole resin systems, so this work has focussed on characterising these properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

The phenolic resole resin Resinox[®] CL1916 and acid catalyst Resinox[®] AH1964F from the Huntsman Chemical Co. Australia Pty Ltd were used in a ratio of 7 parts catalyst to 100 parts resin. Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was performed using a Dupont Instruments 910 Differential Scanning Calorimeter with 15-20 mg samples in hermetically sealed pans. Viscosity measurements were made using a Brookfield DV II digital viscometer with controlled isothermal temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Resin Chemistry

Phenolic resole resins are produced from the alkali-catalysed reaction of phenol and formaldehyde which results in varying degrees of methylol group substitution at the *para* and *ortho* positions of the phenol ring [6]. The resin is primarily the mono-substituted species (eg. **1** in Scheme 3) and when catalysed with an acid, reacts via the formation of benzylic carbonium ions (**2** in Scheme 3), with vacant substitution sites on phenol rings to yield methylene links (**3** in Scheme 3) or with other methylol groups to yield ether links (**4** in Scheme 3). The ether links can then thermally decompose with the release of formaldehyde to yield methylene links, though this occurs at temperatures higher than the usual cure temperatures. The resin also contains 20 - 30 % disubstituted phenols which provide the crosslinking necessary to form a rigid material. Thus, for the production of methylene links, one unit of water is produced for every unit of methylol groups reacted. For the full cure of a phenolic resole resin, this results in approximately 11 wt% water being formed. The variety of different species in the resin and their different reactivities [6] mean that there is no simple mechanistic description of the cure kinetics.

Scheme 3: Acid-catalysed cure reactions of phenolic resole resins

Differential Scanning Calorimetry

The cure of the catalysed resin can be followed by DSC which measures the heat flow from a sample under controlled conditions. The amount of heat flow (dq/dt) is proportional to the rate of chemical reaction ($d[A]/dt$) and the heat of reaction (ΔH_A) as shown in Eqn 1 where A and B refer to different reactions. The integration of Eqn 1 with respect to time yields a value for total heat released and thus the heat of reaction. The cumulative integral also gives a measure of the extent of reaction (α) versus time.

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = \Delta H_A \frac{d[A]}{dt} + \Delta H_B \frac{d[B]}{dt} + \dots \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1 shows heat flow data for a catalysed resin sample during a $5^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ dynamic DSC scan. The curve follows the same trend to that obtained by Focke *et al.* [7] for a similar resin

system with two peaks being evident which is indicative of two separate reactions. The higher temperature peak may result from the thermal decomposition of ether links (2 in Scheme 3) but this has not yet been confirmed by spectroscopic studies. The total heat obtained by integrating the peaks is 346 J.g^{-1} which is significantly higher than the 228 J.g^{-1} obtained by Focke *et al.*, however Gupta *et al.* [8] have shown that the heat of reaction for the cure of phenolic resoles is very sensitive to the pH.

Isothermal DSC measurements can provide accurate kinetic data at the temperatures of interest that closely reflect the conditions used in practice. Fig. 2(a) shows the isothermal heat flow produced by a resin sample cured at 40°C , starting at a maximum and then decreasing rapidly. This is significantly different to what is observed for the cure of polyester and vinyl ester resins which show no significant heat produced until the resin gels. This 'front end' exotherm is significant in relation to RTM processing when Scheme 1 is considered as it means that the major heat effects occur during and just after the filling of a mould.

Fig.1: Dynamic DSC scan at 5°C.min^{-1} of catalysed phenolic resole resin

Fig. 2: DSC of catalysed phenolic resole resin (a) isothermal at 40°C and (b) residual heat scan at 1°C.min^{-1}

Table 1: Heats of reaction (ΔH_{iso} , ΔH_{res} , ΔH_{tot}) and isothermal extent of reaction (α_{iso}) for catalysed phenolic resole resin

Temperature (°C)	ΔH_{iso} (J.g ⁻¹)	ΔH_{res} (J.g ⁻¹)	ΔH_{tot} (J.g ⁻¹)	α_{iso}
35	222	125	347	0.641
40	228	119	347	0.657
45	242	110	352	0.687
50	261	98	359	0.728
55	262	87	349	0.751

The total heat produced at various isothermal temperatures, ΔH_{iso} , are summarised in Table 1. After each isothermal run, the sample was subjected to a 1°C.min⁻¹ dynamic DSC scan to measure the residual heat of reaction, ΔH_{res} (Table 1), and the sum of the two measured heats yields a value for the total heat of reaction, ΔH_{tot} (Table 1). Also shown in Table 1 is the extent of reaction at each isothermal temperature (α_{iso}) calculated using the heats of reaction. The extent of reaction ($\alpha = \Delta H_t / \Delta H_{\text{tot}}$) calculated using the cumulative integral of heat flow ΔH_t and ΔH_{tot} are plotted versus time in Fig. 3. The results show that while the maximum extent of reaction increases with cure temperature, the increase is not large and even at 55°C 25 % remains unreacted. The significance of the extra cure at high temperatures to the matrix properties was investigated by measuring the tensile properties of cast resin cured for 5 h at 40°C and then postcured for 5 h at 80°C. The results (Table 2) show a major increase in properties with postcure which is indicative of an increase in crosslink density. The effective degree of functionality of the phenolic resin is about 1.2 which means that at 70 % conversion the resin matrix is probably more akin to a high molecular weight branched polymer than a crosslinked network, which would explain the low strength and modulus after curing at 40°C. The final 30 % conversion is thus essential to achieving a well crosslinked matrix and this can only be obtained by further cure above about 70°C (see Fig. 2(b)).

Fig 3: Extent of reaction versus cure time for catalysed phenolic resole resin at different temperatures.

Table 2: Tensile properties of cast resin

Cure	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Elongation to Break (%)
5 h at 40°C	10.2	1.37	0.79
5 h at 40°C + 5 h at 80°C	33.4	2.79	1.28

Modelling the filling of a resin transfer mould requires mathematical descriptions of the cure kinetics and their temperature dependence. As discussed earlier, a mechanistic description of the cure kinetics is very complex and thus impractical, so an empirical approach has been adopted. The analysis of the cure profiles revealed that it was necessary to distinguish between a fast reaction that occurs during the initial stage of cure and the remainder of the cure. The early reaction, designated as reaction A which represents 0.08 of the total measured reaction, was found to follow a first order kinetic relationship (Eqn 2) with the rate constant k_A (min^{-1}) described by an Arrhenius relationship (Eqn 3) with temperature, T , in absolute units (K).

$$\frac{d\alpha_A}{dt} = k_A(1 - \alpha_A) \quad (2)$$

$$\ln k_A = -\frac{8199}{T} + 22.56 \quad (3)$$

The remainder of the isothermal cure (i.e. 0.92 of the total), designated as reaction B, can be described by a modified second order kinetic relationship (Eqn 4) in which the rate constant k_B is described by Eqn. 5 and the total isothermal conversion, α_{iso} , calculated using Eqn. 6. There may be a more appropriate form for the kinetic relationship for the cure but Eqns 2 and 4 give very good correlations with the experimental results.

$$\frac{d\alpha_B}{dt} = k_B \left((1 - \alpha_B)^2 - (1 - \alpha_{iso})^2 \right) \quad \text{for } \alpha_B < \alpha_{iso} \quad (4)$$

$$\ln k_B = -\frac{9990}{T} + 28.26 \quad (5)$$

$$\ln \alpha_{iso} = -\frac{846}{T} + 2.29 \quad \text{for } \alpha_{iso} \leq 1 \quad (6)$$

The kinetic relationships enable the reaction rate to be calculated, and thus the extent of reaction, at a particular temperature. Eqn 7 can then be used to calculate the heat flow (W.g^{-1}) generated by a reacting sample which either goes to raising the temperature or is lost through heat transfer.

$$\frac{dq}{dt} = 0.458 \frac{d\alpha_A}{dt} + 5.325 \frac{d\alpha_B}{dt} \quad (7)$$

It should be noted that the kinetic relationships were derived using isothermal data between 35 and 55°C and so do not cover the higher temperature reaction seen in Fig. 1. However the main focus of this work is to describe the resin behaviour during, and immediately following, the filling of a resin transfer mould. The relationship derived for maximum conversion at a particular temperature (Eqn 6) predicts total conversion at 96°C and above, however this assumes the same reaction occurs through to total conversion which as discussed earlier may not be the case. For this type of resin system, a postcure at 80°C is usually recommended, which according to Eqn 6 will only yield a conversion of 0.9. Further work is being undertaken to determine the most appropriate postcure schedule.

Viscosity

The isothermal shear viscosities of the catalysed resin versus time for temperatures between 25 and 45°C are shown in Fig. 4. The viscosity upper limit of 60 Pa.s imposed by the viscometer used is well beyond the values applicable to the filling of a resin transfer mould, which are usually below 1 Pa.s (1000cps). The viscosity increases during cure from the onset and rises rapidly with increasing cure reflecting the fast reaction rate early in the cure observed in the DSC studies.

A plot of the logarithm of shear viscosity, μ , versus time yields a linear relationship as shown in Fig. 5. After an initial decrease due to temperature equalisation, a fast increase in viscosity is observed for a short period before settling into a slower linear increase for the rest of the measured results. The point of crossover from the faster to the slower rate of increase was assigned as occurring at time X_t minutes. The slopes were measured as C_A and C_B for the early and later regions, respectively. The intercepts were also recorded as pseudo initial viscosity values μ_A^0 and μ_B^0 . All these terms follow an Arrhenius type relationship, with correlation coefficients of 0.999 or better. The equations describing the changes in viscosity up to the maximum measured values are shown as Eqns 7-13.

It is notable that the activation energies derived from the Arrhenius equations for the reaction rate constants (Eqns 3 and 5) and the viscosity rate constants (Eqns 9 and 10) summarised in Table 3 correlate closely for the two cure stages. This supports the analytical approach, with the early reaction clearly reflecting a different reaction to the bulk of the cure. The nature of reaction A is not known though it may be the reaction of the 9 % free phenol present in the resin, which may react faster than the substituted phenols and would have a more pronounced effect on the resin viscosity. The faster cure from reaction A is significant for RTM processing as it generates extra heat and a faster viscosity increase during the mould filling stage.

Fig.4: Viscosity versus time for catalysed phenolic resole resin at different isothermal cure temperatures

Fig. 5: Analysis of viscosity data at 35°C.

$$\ln \mu = C_A t + \ln \mu_A^0 \quad \text{for } t < X_t \quad (7)$$

$$\ln \mu = C_B t + \ln \mu_B^0 \quad \text{for } t > X_t \quad (8)$$

$$\ln C_A = -\frac{7579}{T} + 22.49 \quad (9)$$

$$\ln C_B = -\frac{10100}{T} + 30.45 \quad (10)$$

$$\ln \eta_A^0 = \frac{6990}{T} - 17.32 \quad (11)$$

$$\ln \eta_B^0 = \frac{11441}{T} - 31.39 \quad (12)$$

$$\ln X_t = \frac{9971}{T} - 29.75 \quad (13)$$

Table 3: Arrhenius parameters

Term	Activation Energy (kJ.mol ⁻¹)	
	A	B
k (DSC)	68	83
C (viscosity)	63	84

The derived relationships enable the viscosity to be calculated at any time for an isothermal cure. However for use in simulations using a variable temperature, it is necessary to describe a relationship between viscosity and extent of reaction. By interpolating the DSC extent of reaction versus time data to match times with those of the viscosity data, a plot such as Fig. 6(a) for 40°C is obtained. It is important to note however that there is always a degree of uncertainty introduced when combining data collected from different techniques that use different sample masses and environments.

Fig. 6: Plot of (a) viscosity versus extent of reaction (α) and (b) $\ln(\text{viscosity})$ versus $1/(1-\alpha)$ for isothermal cure of catalysed phenolic resole resin at 40°C.

The viscosity of a polymeric fluid is related to its viscosity average molecular weight, M_v , which in turn is related to the number average molecular weight M_n . If it is assumed that up to a conversion of 0.5, the level of crosslinking is small such that the cure can be characterised as a step-growth polymerisation, then M_n can be estimated using the Carothers equation (Eqn 14) where M_0 is the molecular weight of the repeat unit and α is the extent of reaction as described earlier.

$$M_n = \frac{M_0}{(1-\alpha)} \quad (14)$$

A plot of the logarithm of the viscosity versus $1/(1-\alpha)$, as shown for 40°C in Fig. 6(b), gives a linear relationship from which Eqns 15 and 16 were derived. The relationship underestimates the viscosity during the first 10 % conversion which may be due to reaction A, although there may be some errors in the viscosity and DSC data in this region due to warm-up effects. Eqns 15 and 16 are essentially empirical but the term B in Eqn 15 can be viewed as a temperature

shift factor that reflects through Eqn 16 the energy required for molecules to leave their equilibrium position and move across one another. It is quite likely that the relationship breaks down at higher conversions as gelation is approached, but this is irrelevant to RTM processing.

$$\ln \mu = \frac{8.005}{(1-\alpha)} - B \quad (15)$$

$$B = -\frac{8740}{T} + 31.76 \quad (16)$$

RTM Processing

Despite the inherently complex nature of the acid-catalysed cure of phenolic resole resins, it has been possible to derive empirical relationships to describe the cure kinetics and viscosity changes over the temperatures of practical interest for RTM processing. Only one stoichiometry of a commercial resin has been studied, however the approach developed should be applicable to other similar systems. The utility of the derived empirical relationships lies in their predictive capacity for actual RTM processing applications and this can be realised through simulation models that include the physical properties of the reinforcement and mould, the filling pressure and the applied temperature profile [5].

There are some general observations from the results that can be made in relation to the processing of acid-catalysed phenolic resins. Firstly there is the degree of exothermicity of the cure reaction which for total cure is 347 J.g⁻¹. This is sufficient to raise the temperature of the resin (C_p = 2.1 J.g⁻¹.°C⁻¹) by 165°C, or to raise the temperature from 25 to 100°C and then convert 0.12 g of water to steam for every 1 g of resin. However, in practice under stable conditions, it is only the first 60 % of reaction (Fig. 3) which produces 208 J.g⁻¹ that is important. Of course normally the heat effect is much less, as most of the heat is lost to the surroundings, but when the heat flow profile seen in Fig. 2(a) is considered in conjunction with Scheme 1, it is clear why the acid-catalysed phenolic resole resins have short pot lives (eg. 5 min at 20°C for 1kg). The pot life is not a problem in RTM processing if the resin and catalyst are mixed just prior to injection into the mould as this avoids having to handle any bulk catalysed resin. Once the resin is distributed with the reinforcement there is more heat required to raise the temperature, for example with a 50 wt% glass loading a potential increase with no heat loss of 72°C (60 % conversion) is calculated.

The higher temperature cure reaction highlighted by the DSC work (Fig. 2(b)) is essential to the development of satisfactory mechanical properties. While this final reaction can be completed with a postcure after removal from the mould it is probably judicious that a part experiences above 50°C before demoulding. It is thus necessary to have the capacity to heat a resin transfer mould if it is to be used with these resins. An interesting aspect of the cure modelling is that it potentially allows one to determine a temperature schedule that uses the heat produced by the cure to raise the overall temperature to a desired level without additional external heating. However to achieve this a good knowledge of the heat transfer properties of the mould used is needed.

The relevance to RTM processing of the viscosity changes during cure depends on several features related to the part being made. The fill time and maximum injection pressure are important, as when a large part is being made it is necessary to ensure that the viscosity at the

flow front does not increase to a level where a greater pressure than is available is required to complete the filling of the mould. This can be overcome by filling the mould faster using a higher initial injection pressure or by using a lower initial temperature to reduce the rate of viscosity increase, though this will tend to increase the fill time. It is also important to achieve good wet-out of the reinforcement and if the resin flow is too fast, bubbles can get entrapped behind the flow front. This depends on the type and volume fraction of the reinforcement used. It is thus usually necessary to compromise between the fill time, injection pressure and temperature, and such decisions require a knowledge of viscosity changes during filling of a mould.

CONCLUSIONS

The RTM processing of GRP-phenolic composites requires an understanding of the nature of the cure behaviour of phenolic laminating resins which differs in several ways to that of polyester and vinyl ester resins. To facilitate this, the cure of an acid cured phenolic resole resin has been studied using isothermal DSC and viscosity measurements over a range of temperatures and the results have been described by a series of empirical formulas. These empirical formulas can be used to simulate the changes occurring during RTM processing of a particular part which would identify any risks associated with the high exothermicity of the cure reaction. The need for an additional cure step above 70°C to achieve satisfactory physical properties has also been confirmed.

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